

**DIAGNOSTIC VALUE OF ULTRASOUND IN DETECTING DAMAGE TO THE
PELVIC FLOOR MUSCLES AFTER VAGINAL BIRTH**

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Objective: Pelvic organ prolapse, various types of urinary and fecal incontinence, chronic cystourethritis and sexual dysfunction remain one of the most common diseases in urogynecology. 74 patients of different ages were observed. The prevalence of pelvic organ prolapse and prolapse reaches 30%, and in 47.3% of cases, genital prolapse is accompanied by stress urinary incontinence [1, 2]. Currently, pelvic ultrasound is widely used to assess pelvic mobility. The advantages of this method include its availability, the absence of ionizing radiation and its non-invasiveness. In addition, no special preparation of the patient is required. Typically, perineal scanning is used to determine pelvic mobility.

Materials and methods of research: Pelvic floor muscle dysfunction occurs for a number of reasons: age, heredity, birth trauma, large births, heavy physical activity associated with increased intra-abdominal pressure, etc. Recently, there has been a tendency to "rejuvenation" of these disorders [26]. The occurrence of prolapse of the genital organs in young and parous women indicates the role of connective tissue dysplasia in the development of the disease. The combination of organic pathology and pelvic organ prolapse determines a variety of clinical manifestations: sensation of a foreign body in the vagina, involuntary urge to urinate, urinary incontinence with urgency and physical exertion, night and day, a feeling of incomplete emptying of the bladder, a feeling of squeezing, discomfort, heaviness in the perineum and lower abdomen. Many patients have sexual dysfunction and / or dyspareunia. Delayed urination or a feeling of incomplete bladder emptying is often associated with anterior vaginal wall prolapse. Clinical manifestations can develop during reproductive age and throughout life, dramatically reducing quality of life [1,29].

Research results: 74 patients of different ages were observed. Urinary incontinence in women is the most common disease in the structure of pelvic organ dysfunction. Approximately 50% of women aged 45 to 60 years have experienced urinary incontinence at least once. Its prevalence among women is 33.6-36.8%. The situation worsens with age. So, if in the age group

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25 to 34 years this figure reaches 8.7%, then in the age group 55 and older this figure exceeds 34%. Stress urinary incontinence occurs in 70% of cases in women over 50 years, which confirms the social significance of the problem [3]. The actual prevalence of urinary incontinence may be even higher, since women are embarrassed to tell their doctors about this disease and consider it an integral part of aging [4]. In 30-40% of cases, the stress component is combined with the urgency component, that is, a mixed form of urinary incontinence occurs. The prevalence of this type increases with age and reaches 56% after 60 years of age [5]. Urinary incontinence questionnaires are used in urogynecological practice: Urogenital Distress Inventory (UDI-6), Incontinence Impact Questionnaire (IIQ-7), International Incontinence Consultation Questionnaire (ICIQ-SF), International Index of Quality of Life Assessment for Urinary Incontinence, Questionnaire Life SF-36, King's Questionnaire, etc. A standard questionnaire for assessing pelvic organ prolapse and/or female sexual function. Urinary incontinence is considered a component of the Pelvic Organ Prolapse and Urinary Sexual Function Questionnaire (PISQ-31). The PISQ-12 is a shorter version and is recommended for use in clinical practice. The most common method for diagnosing sexual dysfunction is the Female Sexual Function Index (FSFI). In women without prolapse, the increase in its volume during pelvic scanning was 28%, which indicated normal pelvic mobility. At the same time, the studied indicator in patients with asymptomatic pelvic organ prolapse reached 75%. Pathological pelvic mobility, starting from an increase in the volume of the prolapse of 52%, requires further dynamic monitoring of preventive measures to strengthen the pelvic floor muscles (biofeedback technique (BFB)).

Conclusion : Among the new diagnostic equipment, the innovative Vaginal Tactile Imager device is worth noting, which guarantees a quantitative and qualitative assessment of the condition of the pelvic floor muscles. With the help of this device, the pressure, strength and stiffness of the muscles are measured, their condition is monitored during labor and after birth. The latest technology, using a sensitive silicone sensor, allows you to convert tactile sensations into a computer image in real time. The device diagnoses pelvic floor muscle weakness, vaginismus, vulvodynia, prolapse, muscle ruptures during labor and after childbirth, and other pathological changes in the pelvic floor [11,30].

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